

Plasma Density Estimation from Field Line Resonances
in the Magnetosphere

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I hereby certify that the work embodied in this thesis is the result of original research and has not been submitted for a degree to any other University or Institution.

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To Mum and Dad.

Mum, for teaching me to value doing *my* best rather than achieving *the* best.

Dad, for awakening me to the joy of exploring patterns, mathematical beauty, and
the wonder of the physical universe.

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Abstract

When geomagnetic field lines in the Earth's magnetosphere are perturbed they may resonate like a violin string, giving rise to ultra-low frequency (ULF) hydromagnetic wave field line resonance (FLR). Through studying the effect of mass loading on FLR it is possible to remotely determine the plasma mass density in these regions. A number of attempts have previously been made to develop a technique for probing plasmaspheric densities using the harmonic structure of observed ULF field line resonances.

In developing this technique further, the fundamental relationship between flux tube density and FLR harmonic frequencies has been explored. A number of parameterised density models were examined, and the Bernstein basis polynomials were found to be particularly useful due to the spatial significance of the plasma model parameters and the wide variety of possible profiles. FLR harmonics were observed in geomagnetic pulsation data measured by the GOES spacecraft in 2003. The situation with one GOES satellite slowly drifting azimuthally past another provided the opportunity to examine the azimuthal structure of the resonances.

The challenges associated with determining the density profile of a flux tube from FLR harmonic frequencies have been explored. It was found that less information is contained in the harmonic series than has previously been expected.

Chapter 1

Introduction

As the sun produces energy it continually boils off charged particles which stream out into space. This constant “solar wind” flows past the planet and interacts with the Earth’s magnetic field, producing a region beyond the atmosphere in which many of these particles are trapped in a relentless and intricate dance, losing much of their energy in the process.

Understanding this complicated region of near-Earth space is particularly important for communications and space weather. Naturally occurring oscillations may be used to remotely probe the properties of the particles trapped in the Earth’s magnetic field.

1.1 The Near-Earth Environment

The region of space near to the Earth is neither empty nor simple. This environment is filled with a tenuous gas of charged particles in which overall charge neutrality is preserved. Such a material is called a *plasma*, and more than 99% of the matter in the universe exists in this state. Near-Earth space science is a relatively young branch of physics, and the present understanding of this environment is described in a number of reviews [*Troitskaya and Gul'elmi*, 1967; *Orr*, 1973; *Samson*, 1991; *Kivelson and Russell*, 1996; *Olson*, 1999]. The environment known as near-Earth space ranges as far as the solar corona.

The largest scale motion of the interplanetary plasma is a predominantly radial escape of particles from the sun. The ionised gas of the Sun's corona is at a much greater pressure than interstellar space, and this pressure difference is sufficient to force the plasma outward against the restraining influence of solar gravity. This plasma flow was first proposed by *Chapman and Ferraro* [1930] and is called the *solar wind*. Although originally thought to be intermittent, the realisation by *Biermann* [1951] that the solar wind was responsible for the direction of comet tails suggested it was continuous. A theoretical description of the solar wind was established by *Parker* [1958], and the subsequent dawning of the space age enabled experimental confirmation of the solar wind.

The Earth presents both a physical and magnetic obstruction, so that as the solar wind moves past the Earth its flow is diverted and some of the ionised matter is captured by the geomagnetic field. A cavity is created within which the geomagnetic field is the dominant magnetic influence, and this region is called the *magnetosphere*. The outer boundary of the magnetosphere is called the *magnetopause*. A schematic representation of the magnetosphere, indicating important regions and features, is shown in Figure 1.1.

Not all of the field lines leaving the South geomagnetic pole reconnect with the North pole. At very high latitudes the geomagnetic field lines may connect directly to the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF). This produces a region near each pole called the *cusp* where solar wind plasma can directly enter into the magnetosphere.

The magnetosphere is compressed on the sunward side of the Earth and stretched out into a long tail on the opposite side, shaped by a balance of pressure between the outward-flowing solar wind and the geomagnetic field. The stretched region of the magnetosphere on the night side of the Earth may extend up to 1000 Earth radii (R_E) into space and is called the *geomagnetic tail*. It contributes to magnetospheric phenomena by storing plasma and energy which can be released into the inner magnetosphere during periods of high activity known as *magnetospheric substorms*. The tail is divided into a *North lobe* and a *South lobe* by a relatively thin region of hot

Figure 1.1: Important regions and current systems in the magnetosphere, adapted from *Kivelson and Russell [1996]*.

plasma called the *plasma sheet*. A *current sheet* flows in this hot plasma, between the magnetic field that is directed away from Earth (in the South lobe) and the magnetic field directed towards Earth (in the North lobe).

A subregion of the magnetosphere is a roughly toroidal volume of cold ($E_K < 10$ eV) dense ($\rho \approx 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) plasma called the *plasmasphere*. The plasmasphere is inside geosynchronous orbit ($6.6 R_E$) except for extended periods of low magnetic activity, when it expands beyond its normal size. It is generally contained within 3-5 R_E , and the outer boundary of the plasmasphere can be defined by a sharp decrease in the cold plasma density or a more gradual decrease that is not necessarily monotonic. Outside the plasmasphere is a region of low density usually referred to as the *plasmatrough*, and if the decrease is sharp the boundary between the plasmasphere and trough is called the *plasmopause*.

The inner boundary of the plasmasphere is the *ionosphere*, a region at the top of the Earth's atmosphere where neutral particles are ionised by photons and the impact of high energy particles. The ionosphere represents the boundary between Earth's atmosphere and near-Earth space. Below the ionosphere, the atmosphere has low electrical conductivity and is mostly governed by thermal processes. Beyond the ionosphere the electrical conductivity is high and the plasma environment is driven by electromagnetic and interplanetary processes.

Substructure in the density of ionised components with altitude led early observers to divide the ionosphere into three main regions:

- the D region, which is typically below 90 km altitude,
- the E region, which is between 90 and 130 km altitude, and
- the F region which is above 130 km altitude.

The formation of these layers in the ionosphere is explained by the different ionisation mechanisms and absorption energies of various neutral atmosphere constituents. The ionisation is a result of energetic cosmic particles and solar photons giving energy to components of the upper atmosphere. The F region typically has the largest electron density, and thus the highest electrical conductivity.

Sources within the Earth produce an approximately dipolar magnetic field, and this simple approximation is regularly used. The geomagnetic field is, however, distorted in space by currents that derive their energy from the solar wind. Currents flow at the magnetopause as manifestations of the magnetic field distortion. On the sunward side of the magnetosphere the *magnetopause current* flows in an easterly direction. A *tail current* flows at the magnetopause in the geomagnetic tail.

There are also field distorting currents located within the magnetosphere. Gradient and curvature drift, two of the characteristic motions experienced by particles in a magnetised plasma, cause positive particles to drift westward and negative particles to drift eastward. A westward *ring current* is established that tends to decrease the strength of the northward field observed on the Earth's surface, particularly near the equator.

The polar regions also support current systems. *Field-aligned currents* flow down to the polar ionosphere, where the high ionospheric conductivity and atmospheric resistance force the electrical current to flow across the field lines. These field-aligned currents form a circuit involving the ring current and the magnetopause, and near the ionosphere they become involved in auroral phenomena.

While the simple dipole field model is useful for many aspects of near-Earth space studies, the systems of electric current within the magnetosphere accompany magnetic field distortions. Careful observation of these influences has led to statistical models for the geomagnetic field [*Tsyganenko and Stern, 1996; Tsyganenko, 2002*]. The difficulty in modelling the various magnetospheric processes theoretically prevents the creation of a dynamic theoretical magnetic field model.

A large portion of the magnetosphere is composed of cold plasma, but there are a few specific regions that involve higher energy particles such as the Van Allen radiation belts, the ring current, and the auroral zone. The radiation belts overlap the plasmasphere, and it is possible for the particle populations at different energies to be involved in separate processes even within the same volume. Large scale processes can be focused down to small-scale phenomena in the magnetosphere by the converging

magnetic field. Boundaries such as the magnetopause and plasmapause give rise to turbulence as the plasma moves.

These properties give rise to complicated interactions within the magnetosphere. The majority of the plasma is cold, and exhibits both fluid and electromagnetic properties. Such a medium is described by the theory of *magnetohydrodynamics* (MHD). On the Earth's surface the behaviour of gaseous fluids is based on the significance of collisions, but magnetospheric plasma is mostly so tenuous that a reasonable approximation is to regard it as a collisionless medium.

The dynamic nature of near-Earth space gives rise to pulsations in the magnetospheric plasma, and MHD describes both acoustic and electromagnetic waves. In general the electrons and ions behave as distinct components due to different mass and energy, and so there are numerous types of oscillations supported by the plasma. Waves in the magnetosphere are often observed as pulsations in the geomagnetic field.

Of particular interest to this project is the Alfvén wave mode which has field line guided wave energy. Properties of the ionosphere cause the Alfvén wave mode to be reflected at each end of the guiding field line, and so resonances occur which are analogous to those on inhomogeneous stretched strings. Since it is understood that these resonances depend partly on the density of the plasma along the field line, they have been the subject of attempts to remotely probe the magnetosphere mass density.

1.2 Conventions and Nomenclature

It is standard in magnetospheric studies to label magnetic field lines with an *L-value*. For a dipole model field, the *L* parameter is the maximum distance that the field line reaches from the Earth, measured in units of Earth radii R_E , and may be calculated as

$$L = \frac{r_{max}}{R_E} \quad (1.1)$$

The radial distance r traced by a dipole field is given by

$$r = LR_E \cos^2 \lambda \quad (1.2)$$

where λ is the latitude. Therefore, the latitude at which a field line cuts the Earth's surface is given by

$$\lambda_{surface} = \cos^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{L}} \right) \quad (1.3)$$

and so each *L* value corresponds to a particular surface latitude. For this reason field lines are equivalently identified by their latitude ($\lambda_{surface}$) or their *L* value.

Classification	Period (seconds)	Frequency (mHz)
Pc1	0.2 - 5	200 - 5000
Pc2	5 - 10	100 - 200
Pc3	10 - 45	22.2 - 100
Pc4	45 - 150	6.7 - 22.2
Pc5	150 - 600	1.7 - 6.7
Pc6	more than 600	less than 1.7
Pi1	1 - 40	25 - 1000
Pi2	40 - 150	6.7 - 25
Pi3	more than 150	less than 6.7

Table 1.1: Classification scheme for pulsations in the Geomagnetic field. The “Pc” base denotes continuous pulsations and the “Pi” base denotes irregular pulsations. The divisions within each class according to period are mostly arbitrary.

The International Geophysical Year (1958) led to an increase in the study and observation of geomagnetic pulsations, and a classification scheme for the broad range of pulsations was proposed by a subcommittee of the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA) [Jacobs *et al.*, 1964]. This classification was based on two main classes, continuous and irregular pulsations, each of which was grouped according to oscillation period. At the time very little was known about the modes and mechanisms of geomagnetic wave propagation, and there have been subsequent attempts to reclassify pulsations according to the underlying physical processes [Samson, 1991]. However, the original IAGA classification shown in Table 1.1 is still commonly used.

Magnetic field and plasma density properties place the fundamental oscillations of high latitude field lines in the Pc5 band, and plasmaspheric field lines oscillate typically in the Pc3 band. Higher harmonics can be observed as well as these fundamental frequencies, and there exists some ambiguity in labeling these harmonics. Although labeling the lowest possible frequency as the *fundamental* oscillation is universal, some sources call the higher standing frequencies *overtone*s such that the first frequency above the fundamental is the “first overtone”. Throughout this thesis the word *harmonic* is used instead of overtone, and the indexing of the harmonic frequencies is such that the “first harmonic” is the fundamental frequency.

1.3 Project Motivation

It is not easy to measure the density of the core low energy magnetospheric plasma, but this property contributes significantly to our understanding of many magnetosphere processes. Direct measurement techniques clearly require spacecraft observations, but the presence of these instrument platforms affect the local environment.

Information about the energy and density of charged particles is required, and spacecraft accumulate an electric charge that alters the measurements [Tribble, 2003].

Even if the plasma density could be easily measured by a spacecraft in situ, high temporal and spatial resolution density data would require an array of satellites of prohibitive expense. Remote density probing is clearly necessary for accurate and near real-time density measurements.

In general, the propagation of a wave is affected by the medium through which it passes. In theory it is possible to determine features of the medium by observing the behaviour of waves. Alfvén wave resonances on geomagnetic field lines have been used for this purpose in many previous studies (reviewed in Section 2.2.1), probing particularly the plasmasphere and plasmatrough regions.

The wave equation must be solved for frequency eigenvalues (the resonance harmonics), and this is only analytically possible for various ideal approximations. For more realistic situations numerical solutions are required, and this process more naturally provides harmonic frequencies from a specified density profile than it does the reverse process. The latter, which is necessary for remote probing, invariably requires iterative refinement solution techniques. A thorough understanding of the interdependence between frequency eigenvalues and density variation is required in order to understand how much information about the density structure is contained within an observed harmonic series.

1.4 Project Objectives and Thesis Structure

This thesis presents an investigation into the relationship between plasma mass density and Alfvén wave field line resonance frequencies, in an attempt to refine the remote probing techniques currently in use. Chapter 2 presents the theoretical background to plasma oscillations in near-Earth space, and briefly reviews the development of the awareness that continuous geomagnetic pulsations provide mass distribution information.

The behaviour of waves on non-uniform “strings” was modelled, and the results of this investigation are presented in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 documents magnetic field perturbation data obtained by the GOES spacecraft at geosynchronous orbit. The implications of the results found from modelling and in the data are discussed in Chapter 5. This thesis is concluded in Chapter 6.

Chapter 2

Ultra-Low Frequency Plasma Waves

Since more than 99% of the universe exists in the plasma state, scientists have sought a thorough understanding of this state and the processes it supports. Knowledge of the instabilities and waves that are supported by plasmas is important to many areas of physics. Although much is understood about the first order effects in well behaved situations, the intricacies produced by more extreme conditions remain mysterious.

The magnetosphere provides an ideal natural laboratory for the study of plasma. Information about this region was initially provided by studies of those electromagnetic waves which propagated through and/or originated in the space plasma, and were detectable on the Earth's surface. The ability to take in situ measurements with spacecraft significantly expanded magnetospheric studies.

2.1 Plasma Physics

2.1.1 Fundamental Concepts

A plasma has been introduced as a gas of mobile charged particles in which overall charge neutrality is preserved. Plasmas are characterised by collective effects rather than single particle effects, and this is reflected in the following plasma descriptors:

- the potential energy of any charged particle due to its nearest neighbour is much smaller than its kinetic energy,
- the distance between particles is very much smaller than the physical dimensions of the plasma,
- introduced charges are shielded within a distance that is short compared to the dimensions of the plasma, leaving the bulk of the gas electrically neutral.

When a plasma particle is displaced, there is an electric field set up that acts to return the charged particle to its equilibrium position. This restoring force will give rise to harmonic oscillation at a frequency called the *plasma frequency* given by

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{n_0 q^2}{m \epsilon_0}} \quad (2.1)$$

where

n_0 is the number density of the particle species,

q is the charge of the species,

m is the mass of the species,

ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space.

It is apparent that each different particle species in a plasma can have a different characteristic plasma frequency. For a two-component plasma the electron plasma frequency ω_{p_e} and the ion plasma frequency ω_{p_i} are considered separately, and the total plasma frequency is given by

$$\omega_p^2 = \omega_{p_e}^2 + \omega_{p_i}^2 \quad (2.2)$$

In the absence of collisions a free charged particle moving in a magnetic field experiences a central force and thus orbits around a line of magnetic force. The frequency at which the particle gyrates, called the *cyclotron frequency*, is given by

$$\omega_c = \frac{|q|B}{m} \quad (2.3)$$

where B is the magnitude of the magnetic field. Different particle species in a magnetised plasma have different cyclotron frequencies, and particles of opposite charge orbit the field lines in opposite directions.

A magnetised plasma experiences a magnetic pressure P_B given by

$$P_B = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} \quad (2.4)$$

where μ_0 is the permeability of free space. The ratio of the plasma fluid pressure P to magnetic pressure is conventionally represented by the symbol β , where

$$\beta = \frac{P}{\frac{B^2}{2\mu_0}} \quad (2.5)$$

A plasma with $\beta \ll 1$ is called “cold”, and thermal pressure terms are unimportant.

In a collisionless plasma with high conductivity, the electric current density equation requires [Kivelson and Russell, 1996]

$$\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (2.6)$$

Equation (2.6), shows that if $\mathbf{u} \neq 0$ then there must be an electric field present. Consequently, plasma must flow whenever there is an electric field but this does not necessarily result in an electric current. For example, $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ drift causes positive and negative particles to flow in the same direction. It may be shown that the magnetic flux must be frozen into the plasma whenever equation (2.6) is valid. Under these conditions, the flux through a surface of fluid remains constant as the surface moves through the system. Thus it is possible to trace out the field lines that cut through a given surface, and the spatial volume that results is called a *flux tube*.

2.1.2 Properties of Plasma in Near-Earth Space

Throughout the universe, plasmas exist in a wide variety of environments and with different properties. The plasma of near-Earth space is composed primarily of electrons and protons, with small concentrations of helium and oxygen ions. The plasma distributed through most of the Earth’s magnetosphere is considered to be cold and collisionless.

Near-Earth plasma is permeated by the geomagnetic field, and has sufficient conductivity to satisfy equation (2.6). The magnetic field is thus frozen into the plasma, and plasma flow along a flux tube is much easier than across the field from one flux tube to another.

Alfvén and Fälthammar [1963] discussed the motion of a plasma permeated by a magnetic field. When the magnetic field is frozen into a plasma of high conductivity,

a $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ force causes three main effects:

1. Bundles of magnetic field lines resist any effort to compress them laterally;
2. Magnetic field lines shorten as far as the compressibility of the plasma permits due to longitudinal tension;
3. The pressure and tension mean that magnetic field lines displaced from equilibrium will experience a restoring force.

A restoring force gives rise to oscillatory motion, and these effects allow magnetic field lines to be described analogously to oscillating strings.

The flux tubes on which various MHD waves oscillate are shaped by the geomagnetic field geometry. This project is mainly concerned with data from geosynchronous orbits, which are associated with dipole field lines of $L = 6.6$ that have surface footprints at 67° latitude. The field aligned currents shown in Figure 1.1 are thought to be spatially separated and are identified as two current systems. Collectively these are known as the *Birkeland* currents. *Region 1* currents flow between the magnetopause and the ionosphere along high latitude field lines, and *Region 2* currents flow between the ring current and the ionosphere. At the ionosphere, field lines that map from geosynchronous orbit pass through the latitudinal range in which region 2 currents are thought to flow. Since they are field-aligned their effect is to shear the magnetic field azimuthally. The influence of Region 2 currents on the remote sensing technique in this project is discussed in Section 2.2.1.

2.1.3 Plasma Perturbations

The mathematical formulation that describes plasma perturbations in near-Earth space combines equations from electrodynamics and fluid continuity and pressure into the theory of magnetohydrodynamics .

In differential form, Maxwell's equations for electrodynamics are

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu \mathbf{J} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \quad (2.7)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (2.8)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (2.9)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\delta}{\epsilon} \quad (2.10)$$

where

- \mathbf{B} is the magnetic field,
- \mathbf{E} is the electric field,
- \mathbf{J} is the current density,
- δ is the charge density,
- c is the speed of light in a vacuum.

In magnetohydrodynamics the displacement current can be neglected for waves travelling at a speed much less than the speed of light [Cowling, 1957]. Therefore equation (2.7) becomes

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu \mathbf{J} \quad (2.11)$$

Ohm's law provides the current density \mathbf{J} given by

$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (2.12)$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity.

As a collection of particles, a plasma is also described by fluid equations. The fluid equation of motion (also called the *momentum transfer* equation) is essentially Newton's second law for all the forces acting on an element of fluid;

$$mn \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) = qn (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) - \nabla P - \frac{mn(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}_0)}{\tau} \quad (2.13)$$

where

- m is the mass of a particle,
- n is the number density of particles,
- q is the charge of a particle,
- P is the pressure,
- τ is the time between particle collisions.

In equation (2.13) the first term on the right hand side is the Lorentz force, the second term describes the pressure, and the last term describes the effect of collisions. In the near-Earth space environment, equation (2.13) is often simplified by neglecting the collision term. For cold plasmas the pressure term is also neglected. We generally consider one equation for each of the ion and electron gases, as these can have different properties.

The continuity equation relates the flow of material into a given volume to the amount of material leaving that volume. For an environment without sources or sinks of particles, the continuity equation is generally given as

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + (\nabla \cdot n\mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (2.14)$$

Equation (2.14) essentially states that the rate of change of the number of particles in a volume is equal to the outward flux.

The equation of state relates the pressure P and the number of particles n , and comes from kinetic molecular theory. It is usually written as

$$P = n\gamma kT \quad (2.15)$$

where

$$\gamma = \frac{2 + N}{N} \quad (2.16)$$

is the ratio of specific heat at constant pressure to that at constant volume, and

k is Boltzmann's constant,

T is the kinetic temperature,

N is the number of degrees of freedom (3 for 3D space).

Equations (2.7) to (2.12) describe the electromagnetic properties, and equations (2.13) to (2.15) describe the fluid properties of a plasma. The theory of magnetohydrodynamics combines all of these to describe plasma oscillations. The general wave equation was given by *Waters* [1992] as

$$\mathbf{v} \left(\frac{(\mathbf{B}_0 \cdot \mathbf{k})^2}{\mu} - \omega^2 \rho_0 \right) + \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{B}_0^2}{\mu} + \gamma P_0 \right) \mathbf{k} - \frac{(\mathbf{B}_0 \cdot \mathbf{k})}{\mu} \right) (\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{v}) - \frac{(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{B}_0) (\mathbf{B}_0 \cdot \mathbf{v}) \mathbf{k}}{\mu} = 0 \quad (2.17)$$

A comprehensive MHD treatment for uniform homogeneous plasma and magnetic field reveals that there are analytical solutions for three ideal wave modes in the low frequency limit where $\omega \ll \omega_c$ [*Alfvén*, 1942]:

1. The slow mode, which occurs in a plasma where the plasma pressure is significant compared to the magnetic pressure ($\beta \gtrsim 1$). This mode is a compressional wave and its wave vector k is directed along the ambient field. This mode does not contribute to the resonance phenomena discussed in this project;
2. The fast mode, also known as the compressional or magnetosonic mode, trans-

ports energy in the direction of propagation. In general this is not along the ambient field. For a cold plasma the magnetic pressure allows the propagation of this compressional wave. In the absence of a background magnetic field, this mode can travel through warm plasmas as a purely acoustic wave (where collisions allow propagation);

3. The shear Alfvén mode, having a Poynting vector parallel to the background magnetic field \mathbf{B}_0 , is sometimes referred to as the guided mode. The magnetic perturbation and plasma movement are both perpendicular to \mathbf{B}_0 . It is this mode that reflects from the ionosphere and sets up field line resonances.

The magnetic field in the magnetosphere is non-uniform and can be approximated by a dipole geometry for most of the magnetosphere. This inhomogeneity causes the Alfvén and fast modes to couple. *Dungey* [1954] derived the coupled wave equations for a dipole magnetic field by combining Maxwell’s equations and the MHD equations in spherical coordinates. The set of equations he obtained have not yet been solved analytically except for a few special cases, namely:

1. The axially symmetric toroidal mode describing a transverse oscillation in which complete magnetic L shells perform torsional oscillations. The magnetic field is not compressed, and moves azimuthally with the plasma, while the electric field oscillates radially. Since each L shell is assumed to be decoupled, this mode has a latitude-dependent period. The first three harmonics for a shear Alfvén mode are shown schematically in Figure 2.1;
2. The axially symmetric poloidal mode describing a compressional wave in which the whole magnetosphere “breathes” in and out. The period is independent of latitude, and the plasma and magnetic field oscillate radially while the electric field is perturbed azimuthally. The first three harmonics for this Alfvén mode are shown schematically in Figure 2.2;
3. The guided poloidal mode which is similar to the poloidal mode except that the disturbance has a large azimuthal wavenumber and so is highly localised in longitude. Each meridian plane is decoupled.

2.1.4 Field Line Resonance

The phenomena discussed in this thesis are based on the shear Alfvén mode, which is a low frequency electromagnetic wave where the energy is *field line guided*. To obtain the shear Alfvén wave equation, it is necessary to assume that:

- the waves oscillate at low frequencies (much lower than the *ion cyclotron* frequency) so that the MHD wave equations apply, and

Figure 2.1: Axially symmetric toroidal Alfvén mode, showing (a) the fundamental mode, (b) the second harmonic and (c) the third harmonic. The oscillations are purely azimuthal. The field lines shown have a dipole geometry, and the perturbations are sinusoidal (corresponding to the simple case of uniform density and magnetic field). The solid red flux tubes represent the unperturbed equilibrium position, and the slightly pinker and more orange tubes represent each extreme of the oscillation displacement. Notice that the field lines oscillate in phase around the globe.

Figure 2.2: Axially symmetric poloidal Alfvén mode, showing (a) the fundamental mode, (b) the second harmonic and (c) the third harmonic. The oscillations are in a radial direction, and the field lines are stretched and compressed. The field lines shown have a dipole geometry, and the perturbations are purely sinusoidal (corresponding to the simple case of uniform density and magnetic field). The solid red flux tubes represent the unperturbed equilibrium position, and the slightly pinker and more orange tubes represent each extreme of the oscillation displacement. Again the field lines oscillate in phase around the globe.

- the perturbation magnetic field, \mathbf{b} , is much smaller than the background field (the *linear approximation*).

Taking these conditions into account, it may be shown that the dispersion relation is given by [Alfvén, 1942]

$$\frac{\omega^2}{k^2} = \frac{B_0^2}{\rho\mu_0} \quad (2.18)$$

from which it is clear that the phase velocity is given by

$$\begin{aligned} v_{ph} &= \frac{\omega}{k} \\ \text{ie } v_A &= \frac{B_0}{\sqrt{\rho\mu_0}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

where v_A denotes the *Alfvén velocity*. Field line resonance (FLR) between conjugate ionospheres requires reflecting boundaries, and depends on field line length, field magnitude and plasma mass loading. The *Alfvén* velocity contains the field magnitude and plasma mass loading, and influences the resonant frequencies. The low latitude limit for detecting FLRs seems to be at about $L \approx 1.3$ [Menk *et al.*, 2000].

Early in the study of geomagnetic pulsations, it was assumed that the Earth's surface provided the reflective boundary for FLRs. This allowed easy estimation of the field line length. In more recent times the use of spacecraft measurements has promoted discussion about the location of the FLR boundary. Most often it is assumed that the high electrical conductivity of the ionosphere provides a perfectly reflecting boundary, and so to a first order approximation it can be assumed that the F-region provides the reflection point. In pragmatic terms, the difference in field line length between conjugate points on the ground and conjugate points in the ionosphere is negligible for a magnetic field line passing through geosynchronous orbit.

2.2 The Study of Geomagnetic Perturbations

Almost a century after continuous pulsations in the geomagnetic field were first recorded and analysed [Stewart, 1861], they were interpreted as oscillations of entire flux tubes [Dungey, 1954]. This interpretation followed the realisation that the Earth was surrounded by plasma [Storey, 1953], and gave rise to the idea that geomagnetic pulsations could yield information about near-Earth space [Obayashi and Jacobs, 1958; Gul'yel'mi, 1966; Troitskaya and Gul'elmi, 1967; Kitamura and Jacobs, 1968].

2.2.1 Probing the Mass Density

There have been many attempts to use the harmonic frequency structure of ULF resonances to determine plasma mass density in the plasmasphere and magnetosphere. The earliest involved the estimation of equatorial profiles of plasma density from the latitudinal variation of resonant frequencies detected by ground based magnetometers [*Obayashi and Jacobs*, 1958; *Gul'yel'mi*, 1966].

Early spacecraft allowed direct ion density measurements to be made in various regions of the magnetosphere. Data from the Lunik II [*Gringauz*, 1961], OGO-A [*Obayashi*, 1965], and IMP I and II [*Serbu and Mainer*, 1966] satellites suggested electron and ion densities of about 10^3 cm^{-3} for low L -values (2-3) decreasing to about 10^2 cm^{-3} at $L \approx 4$ and remaining of the order of 10 cm^{-3} out to a distance of $L = 9$. *Chappell et al.* [1970] used a mass spectrometer on board the OGO 5 spacecraft to measure the concentrations of H^+ , He^+ , and O^+ ions from an initial perigee height of about 300 km to an apogee of $23 R_E$. Typical results from this study, showing ion concentration as a function of geocentric radius, are shown in Figure 2.3. Although this study was primarily interested in determining characteristics of the plasmasphere, the results contributed to the acceptance of density models which were inversely proportional to powers of radial distance from Earth.

Spacecraft were also able to record ULF resonant signatures in magnetometer data. One of the earliest of these investigations reported transverse ULF oscillations in the magnetic field recorded at the geosynchronous ATS 1 spacecraft [*Cummings et al.*, 1969]. They interpreted their data in terms of FLRs and modelled the oscillations as shear Alfvén waves. They assumed a perfectly conducting Earth, dipole background magnetic field, and a power law density variation of the form

$$\rho = \rho_{eq} \left(\frac{LR_E}{r} \right)^\alpha \quad (2.20)$$

where

ρ_{eq} is the density on the field line at the magnetic equator,

R_E is the Earth's radius,

r is the radial distance to a point on the field line.

Numerical solutions for the poloidal and toroidal wave equations at $L = 6.6$ were given for a fixed ρ_{eq} of 1 amu per cubic centimetre and seven different values of α in equation (2.20). These α values ranged from 0, which is a special case giving uniform density, to 6, which is a special case giving almost constant Alfvén velocity. It was found that the poloidal and toroidal frequencies were almost identical, particularly for harmonics above the fundamental.

Figure 2.3: A typical inbound plasmopause crossing by OGO 5 showing ion concentrations as a function of L , after *Chappell et al.* [1970].

Orr and Matthew [1971] computed the FLR frequencies for poloidal and toroidal modes for a range of density distributions at a variety of latitudes. They found that in general the resonant frequencies for these two modes differ by about 30% for the fundamental and much less for subsequent harmonics.

Samson et al. [1971] presented observations from a latitude chain of 7 magnetic stations in Canada and showed that they implied that much of the geomagnetic pulsation energy was “distributed in the toroidal mode of eigenoscillations of the geomagnetic lines of force”. They also demonstrated that the sense of polarisation switched around 1200-1400 LT, strongly suggesting that the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability at the magnetopause was the generating source of Pc pulsations. The Kelvin-Helmholtz instability occurs in a boundary between fluids of different viscosity flowing past each other, and for example gives rise to surface waves when wind blows over water.

Following these observations, theoretical explanations of excitation mechanisms were proposed [*Chen and Hasegawa*, 1974; *Southwood*, 1974]. It was shown how the energy from Kelvin-Helmholtz surface waves at the magnetopause could couple via the fast mode to transverse resonances on field lines within the magnetosphere.

Singer et al. [1981] gave a general form of the FLR wave equation, suitable for any field line geometry, as (with a misprint in their equation corrected [*Waters et al.*, 1995])

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial s^2} \left(\frac{\xi_\alpha}{h_\alpha} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \ln (h_\alpha^2 B_0) \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{\xi_\alpha}{h_\alpha} \right) + \frac{\mu_0 \rho \omega^2}{B_0^2} \left(\frac{\xi_\alpha}{h_\alpha} \right) = 0 \quad (2.21)$$

where

- s is the distance along the field line,
- ξ_α is the plasma displacement in the $\hat{\alpha}$ direction,
- h_α is the normal separation between adjacent field lines,
- B_0 is the static magnetic field strength,
- ρ is the plasma mass density,
- ω is the frequency of oscillation.

Equation (2.21) is in one dimension and applies to strictly transverse oscillations. Also, the way that this equation is derived from the linearised MHD equations neglects the term which describes effects arising from background electrical currents. In this way the effects of the coincidence of geosynchronous field lines with region 2 Birkeland currents in the ionosphere are assumed to be insignificant.

The development of a technique for identifying resonant eigenfrequencies using

the cross spectral phase of data recorded by closely spaced ground stations enabled accurate determination of FLR harmonics [Waters *et al.*, 1991]. This rekindled interest in using ULF resonances for remote density probing.

Price *et al.* [1999] adapted equation (2.21) for a dipole field geometry to give

$$\frac{d^2}{d\lambda^2} \left(\frac{\xi}{h} \right) + \tan \lambda \frac{d}{d\lambda} \left(\frac{\xi}{h} \right) + \frac{\mu_0 \omega^2 L^8 R_E^8}{K^2} \rho(\lambda) \cos^{14} \lambda \left(\frac{\xi}{h} \right) = 0 \quad (2.22)$$

where

λ is the latitude,

K is the Earth's magnetic moment.

They developed a technique for estimating the density at discrete locations along the field line corresponding to the number of observed harmonics.

There have been a number of recent studies that have assumed a functional form for the density profile along a field line and varied the model parameters to yield frequencies that match observed harmonics. Models other than the power law, with more than two parameters, were proposed by Denton *et al.* [2001] and are discussed in Section 3.4.2. Due to its long-standing acceptance, the power law remains in use, and considerable effort has been made to identify the most appropriate exponent, α , to use in the model for particular regions of the magnetosphere. It has been suggested that some events, where the power law seems inadequate, indicate an equatorial mass density enhancement [Denton *et al.*, 2004; Takahashi *et al.*, 2004; Denton *et al.*, 2006; Takahashi *et al.*, 2006]. These recent developments are the topic of considerable discussion in Chapter 5.

2.2.2 Longitudinal Phase Variations

The toroidal mode for the shear Alfvén wave involves complete L -shells oscillating in phase, as shown in Figure 2.1. Such an ideal mode of oscillation is unlikely due to the dynamic nature of the magnetosphere and its irregularities. The longitudinal structure of ULF oscillations provides clues about the wave generation mechanisms.

A first approximation considers the field geometry in the equatorial plane, where lines of constant flux trace a circle. It is natural to model azimuthal variations by assuming variation of the form $e^{im\phi}$, where ϕ is the longitude and m is the *azimuthal wavenumber* [Olson and Rostoker, 1978]. The azimuthal wavenumber can be thought of as the number of complete wavelengths around the L -shell, so $m = 1$ corresponds to a phase change of 1 degree with each longitudinal degree of angular separation. In this description, the ideal toroidal mode is said to have $m = 0$.

The azimuthal wave number can easily be determined from the phase difference

between measurements taken at two longitudinal locations. *Olson and Rostoker* [1978] gave the relationship between phase difference and m number as

$$m = \frac{2\pi R \Delta\phi}{360S} \cos \lambda \quad (2.23)$$

where R is the radius (Earth's radius for ground stations), S is the station separation, $\Delta\phi$ is the estimated phase difference in degrees and λ is the station latitude.

For geosynchronous spacecraft measurements it is possible to determine m by comparing the cross phase directly with the longitudinal position of the satellites. For such measurements,

$$m = \frac{\Delta\phi}{|\phi_2 - \phi_1|} \quad (2.24)$$

where ϕ_2 and ϕ_1 are the longitudes of the two satellites.

Low m values ($m \lesssim 20$) are consistent with wave generation by Kelvin-Helmholtz instabilities at boundaries such as the magnetopause. High m values ($m \gtrsim 30$) suggest that the FLR oscillations have their energy sourced from drift and drift-bounce resonance interactions [*Yeoman and Wright, 2001*].

Chapter 3

Resonances on Non-uniform “Strings”

Resonances and harmonic behaviour in inhomogeneous media are difficult to study theoretically. The differential equations quickly become analytically unsolvable, and the two approximations commonly used to enable such solutions represent opposite extremes. For small numbers of discrete steps in the density, a study of partial reflections from each step is possible. In the opposite case, the WKB approximation provides useful solutions under circumstances when the density varies so slowly that partial reflections are insignificant. An understanding of the behaviour of resonance harmonics in inhomogeneous media is essential for determining how measured FLR harmonics may provide mass density estimates in the magnetosphere.

3.1 Introduction

Analytical solutions for each plasma oscillation mode have been derived for the special case of uniform density and background magnetic field, but the near-Earth magnetospheric environment provides neither of these luxuries. The geomagnetic field is curved and varies in strength, and the plasma density varies across the different regions of the magnetosphere. For these reasons, geomagnetic field line resonances differ from the vibrations of simple violin strings.

All remote sensing techniques that estimate the plasma mass density from observed FLR harmonics are built on the relationship between density variations and the harmonic frequencies. Modelling the behaviour of resonances in non-uniform media allowed properties of this relationship to be determined.

3.2 Waves

The simplest form of the wave equation describes an undamped wave on a uniform string, and is given by

$$\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\rho}{F} \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} \quad (3.1)$$

where y is the displacement of the string due to the wave, x is the position along the string, t is time, ρ is the linear density of the string and F is a constant describing the restoring force. The restoring force for simple strings is due to the tension. The waveforms are sinusoidal in time and space, as may be easily determined by solving (3.1) using the separation of variables technique. For a string with fixed ends, the spatial boundary conditions give rise to particular sinusoidal eigenfunctions which describe the resonant frequencies.

It is easy to modify this equation to describe an undamped wave on an inhomogeneous straight string by making the density a function of position,

$$\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\rho(x)}{F} \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} \quad (3.2)$$

Although only slightly modified from the simple case, this differential is analytically unsolvable except for special functional forms of $\rho(x)$. Most of the more complicated differential equations describing plasma oscillations in the magnetosphere are also analytically unsolvable and must also be solved numerically.

3.3 Numerical Solutions

As stated, numerical solution methods are required for solving wave DEs where the velocity varies with position. A convenient way to find frequency eigenvalues for a given boundary-value problem is the finite difference matrix technique.

A square matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1j} & \dots \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2j} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \\ a_{i1} & a_{i2} & \dots & a_{ij} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix}$$

has eigenvalues λ where

$$\begin{aligned} A\mathbf{x} &= \lambda\mathbf{x} \\ \text{ie } (\lambda I - A)\mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

Non-trivial solutions to this matrix equation may be found by solving

$$|\lambda I - A| = 0$$

which is, for the matrix A above,

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} \lambda - a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1j} & \dots \\ a_{21} & \lambda - a_{22} & \dots & a_{2j} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \\ a_{i1} & a_{i2} & \dots & \lambda - a_{ij} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

Taking the FLR wave equation for a dipole field geometry given in (2.22), from *Price et al.* [1999], and substituting the finite difference approximations

$$\frac{dy}{d\lambda} = \frac{y(\lambda_{i+1}) - y(\lambda_{i-1})}{2d}$$

and

$$\frac{d^2y}{d\lambda^2} = \frac{y(\lambda_{i+1}) - 2y(\lambda_i) + y(\lambda_{i-1}))}{d^2}$$

it is straightforward to obtain the discrete equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{d^2} + \frac{\tan \lambda_i}{2d}\right) y(\lambda_{i+1}) + \left(\omega^2 \frac{\mu L^8 R_E^8}{K^2} \cos^{14}(\lambda_i) \rho(\lambda_i) - \frac{2}{d^2}\right) y(\lambda_i) + \left(\frac{1}{d^2} - \frac{\tan \lambda_i}{2d}\right) y(\lambda_{i+1}) = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

Writing

$$q_i = \frac{\mu L^8 R_E^8}{K^2} \cos^{14}(\lambda_i) \rho(\lambda_i)$$

for convenience, and choosing $y(x_0) = y(x_{N+1}) = 0$ to yield standing solutions, the set of equations described by (3.4) can be represented as the matrix equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} \omega^2 - \frac{2}{q_1 d^2} & \frac{1}{q_1} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} + \frac{\tan \lambda_1}{2d}\right) & 0 & \dots \\ \frac{1}{q_2} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} - \frac{\tan \lambda_2}{2d}\right) & \omega^2 - \frac{2}{q_2 d^2} & \frac{1}{q_2} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} + \frac{\tan \lambda_2}{2d}\right) & \dots \\ \vdots & & & \\ 0 & \dots & \frac{1}{q_N} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} - \frac{\tan \lambda_N}{2d}\right) & \omega^2 - \frac{2}{q_N d^2} \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{0}$$

This is of the same form as equation (3.3) where ω^2 are the eigenvalues of the matrix A given by

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2}{q_1 d^2} & -\frac{1}{q_1} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} + \frac{\tan \lambda_1}{2d}\right) & 0 & \dots \\ -\frac{1}{q_2} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} - \frac{\tan \lambda_2}{2d}\right) & \frac{2}{q_2 d^2} & -\frac{1}{q_2} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} + \frac{\tan \lambda_2}{2d}\right) & \dots \\ \vdots & & & \\ 0 & \dots & -\frac{1}{q_N} \left(\frac{1}{d^2} - \frac{\tan \lambda_N}{2d}\right) & \frac{2}{q_N d^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

It is straightforward, although often computationally demanding, to use standard linear algebra algorithms to find the eigenvalues of a matrix such as A . The positive square root of these eigenvalues give the resonant frequencies, and since by definition frequency increases monotonically with harmonic order it is easy to order the eigenvalues.

3.4 Modelling Field Line Density Profiles

3.4.1 First Principles Digital Derivation of Density

The harmonic derived density (HARDD) technique developed by *Price et al.* [1999] was a unique attempt to estimate plasmaspheric densities without the use of an assumed model for the form of the density profile. The basis of the technique was to solve the finite difference matrix equation (3.5) for a matrix small enough to have only

one density value for each observed harmonic frequency. In practice, hemispherical symmetry was assumed and so it was possible to determine the density at twice as many discrete locations.

The cost of avoiding a functional form for the density profile along a field line was low spatial resolution due to only the first few harmonics being observed. Also, since the finite difference formulation more closely approximates the FLR wave equation as the step size decreases, the low number of sample sites available for typical HARDD calculations limits the accuracy of solutions.

To overcome some of the stability difficulties encountered in HARDD calculations, *Price et al.* [1999] suggested that more density information would be provided by creating a functional density model where the number of parameters in the model could be matched to the number of harmonics in the same way as the HARDD technique matched the number of sample sites.

3.4.2 Existing Models

In order to attain arbitrary density resolution, many studies model the density profile as a function of position along the field line. The most commonly used functional model of the density profile along a field line is the power law given in equation (2.20). Having only two parameters, ρ_{eq} and α , this model may be used even when few harmonics are observed. By assuming a reasonable value for one of the parameters, the power law model has even been used when only the fundamental harmonic has been measured. Typically the exponent α has been assumed and the equatorial density then determined. This has led to a discussion in the literature about the most appropriate α values for field lines in different L -regions [e.g. *Angerami and Carpenter*, 1966; *Goldstein et al.*, 2001; *Takahashi et al.*, 2004; *Denton et al.*, 2006].

Denton et al. [2001] proposed two density models given by functions of the coordinate z defined by

$$z = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r}{LR_E}} \quad . \quad (3.6)$$

The coordinate z enables Singer's wave equation (2.21) to be separated into two terms [*Radoski*, 1966], and was used as a convenient function of r . The first functional form proposed for the mass density was a polynomial for log of the density where

$$\log_{10} \rho = c_0 + c_2 z^2 + c_4 z^4 \quad (3.7)$$

and the second was an ordinary polynomial of the form

$$\rho = d_0 + d_2 z^2 + d_4 z^4 \quad . \quad (3.8)$$

Figure 3.1: Typical explanation of harmonic dependence on local density, adapted from *Takahashi* [2006]. A change in density at the middle of a string affects the fundamental harmonic (a) which has an antinode where the density change occurred, but does not alter the frequency of the second harmonic due to its node at that point.

The parameters c_i and d_i were adjusted to vary the respective density profiles. There was very little discussion into why these particular functions were desirable for modelling the density profile along a geomagnetic flux tube. The absence of odd powers of z was due to the assumption of hemispherical symmetry.

For no apparent reason, the model in equation (3.7) has subsequently been widely used [*Takahashi et al.*, 2004; *Denton et al.*, 2004] while that in equation (3.8) has been essentially discarded. It has often been claimed that the different frequency responses of harmonics to localised mass density variations are due to their different nodal structure [*Denton et al.*, 2001; *Takahashi et al.*, 2004; *Denton et al.*, 2004; *Takahashi et al.*, 2006; *Takahashi*, 2006]. This idea is represented diagrammatically in Figure 3.1. Studies that present this understanding of frequency dependence on density claim that the independence with which harmonics respond to density variations means that observing more harmonics allows more parameters to be introduced to a density model.

3.4.3 Bernstein Bases for Density Profile

A well-suited field line mass density model would be based on the requirements of this application, and might include the following features:

- an ability to allow hemisphere asymmetry while easily reducing to the symmetric case,
- parameters that adjust to allow a maximum flexibility of density variations on various spatial scales,
- parameters that all contribute actively to the final density form, and

- spatially significant parameters.

Creating a density profile from Bernstein bases provides the luxury of spatially significant parameters, and gives a necessarily smooth and continuous profile. Such density profile parameters are suitable for exploring the response of the harmonic frequencies to density alterations at different locations.

Bernstein bases of order n are constructed by raising both sides of

$$1 = t + (1 - t)$$

to the power n . The right hand side gives $n + 1$ polynomials which form the required basis, and with their natural coefficients they sum to unity at every value of t . The domain of these basis polynomials is the interval $[0, 1]$, but an arbitrary domain can easily be rescaled to satisfy this requirement.

For Bernstein bases of a particular order, the endpoint values of any linear combination are determined by only one basis coefficient each. Every basis polynomial except for the first and last go to zero at both $t = 0$ and $t = 1$. This property, called *endpoint interpolation*, is useful for creating a smooth curve between two fixed points. The well known *Bezier* curves used in computer graphics are typically created using the Bernstein basis of order 3.

The modelling techniques used in this study to explore the relationship between density and resonant frequencies have utilised the Bernstein basis of order 6 to create the density model given by

$$\begin{aligned} \rho = & A_0 t^6 + 6A_1 t^5(1 - t) + 15A_2 t^4(1 - t)^2 + 20A_3 t^3(1 - t)^3 \\ & + 15A_4 t^2(1 - t)^4 + 6A_5 t(1 - t)^5 + A_6(1 - t)^6 \quad . \quad (3.9) \end{aligned}$$

The 7 basis functions which contribute to this density model are shown in Figure 3.2, and the spatial significance of the parameters $\{A_i\}$ is immediately evident. Hemispherical symmetry is obtained by setting

$$\begin{aligned} A_0 &= A_6 \\ A_1 &= A_5 \\ A_2 &= A_4 \end{aligned}$$

This reduces the the 7-parameter model to a 4-parameter model, making the model much easier to apply.

The order 6 Bernstein basis was chosen for a number of reasons. Firstly, a basis of even order was desired so that there would be an odd number of basis polynomials and thus a “middle” one. In order to identify the relationship between localised

Figure 3.2: Bernstein bases of order 6. There are 7 functions, with equally spaced spatial emphasis.

density variations and the resonant frequencies, a density model with parameters controlling fine spatial regions is most useful.

Other considerations placed limits on the number of parameters. Most previous studies have assumed that the number of parameters in the density model should match the number of observed FLR harmonics. The very best events examined in this project were thought to show 6 or 7 harmonics, and so this placed a practical upper limit on the number of parameters. The process of obtaining density from resonant frequencies involves iterative solution schemes, and increasing the number of independent parameters sought reduces the likelihood of convergence. Previous studies have had to limit the parameters in their model to less than the number of observed harmonics for this reason [Denton *et al.*, 2001]. The choice of a 7-parameter model was found to be a good trade-off between these various requirements.

3.5 Behaviour of the Harmonics

3.5.1 The Harmonic Series

As noted, when conditions in a medium allow waves to resonate there is a set of frequency eigenvalues corresponding to standing waves. These harmonics may be arranged in order of increasing frequency to form the *harmonic series*. A good way to visualise the harmonic series is to plot harmonic frequency against harmonic order. For evenly spaced harmonics, such as those which occur on a simple uniform violin string, these points would be collinear and the line on which they sit would pass through the origin. There are a number of ways that a harmonic series could deviate

from this form:

- A change to the environment which caused the harmonics to respond independently could cause the harmonic series to become non-linear. Of course, the harmonic series must always increase monotonically otherwise the order assigned to each frequency would be reallocated to restore monotonicity.
- The harmonic series could remain linear, but its extrapolated intercept on the frequency axis could deviate from zero.

The papers which report the idea represented in Figure 3.1 assume that FLR harmonics vary independently with changes in density profile, which would result in non-linear harmonic series. Other studies have concluded that the harmonic series remain essentially linear for various non-uniform density profiles [Schulz, 1996]. The natural consequence of such evenly spaced harmonics is that any observed spectrum of eigenfrequencies “can yield at most two parameters characteristic of the plasma-density distribution along the field line of interest” [Schulz, 1996], corresponding to the slope and intercept of the linear harmonic series.

3.5.2 The WKB Time of Flight Approximation

A common way to deal with waves in inhomogeneous media is the WKB approximation, which is usually considered to be valid where the scale size of the oscillations is much smaller than the scale size of the system. The conditions which justify the WKB approximation are the same as those under which the time of flight approximation is valid [Sinha and Rajaram, 1997; Schulz, 1996; Takahashi et al., 2004].

Under the time of flight approximation for a shear Alfvén wave, the period of the n th harmonic is given by

$$T_n = \frac{2}{n} \oint \frac{\sqrt{\mu_0 \rho}}{B} ds \quad (3.10)$$

where the integral is along the entire oscillating length of the field line [Poulter et al., 1988]. This integral simply states that the resonant periods are those which fit neatly into the total time it takes to complete a round trip.

Adjusting the density of some portion of the medium will change the speed of all waves passing through that region, regardless of where their nodes are located, and thus uniformly affect the time of flight for all harmonics. Thus the harmonic frequencies will be evenly spaced for *any* combination of density and magnetic field profiles that satisfy the time of flight approximation requirements. However, magnetospheric plasma does not completely satisfy the WKB conditions since low FLR

Figure 3.3: String with single step in linear density. The step is in the middle of the string, and on the left $\rho = 1$ while on the right $\rho = 4$.

harmonics, particularly, have a wavelength comparable to the scale size of the geomagnetic system.

Sinha and Rajaram [1997] analysed the effectiveness of the WKB approximation for FLRs and found that the accuracy of the frequency solutions did not improve with increasing harmonic number. They suggested that the failure of the solution was due to analytical singularities at the reflection boundaries rather than simply the large scale size of the fundamental mode. They found that the WKB method was not finite at the turning points, and gave increasingly unnatural solutions as the distance along the field line from the equator increased. They provided a solution which was finite and continuous at the turning points. Remarkably, even when the WKB approximation does not seem to be valid the harmonic frequencies remain close to evenly spaced [*Schulz, 1996; Poulter et al., 1988*].

Another property of the WKB approximation involves its prediction that no partial reflections are set up because of the wave conserving energy as it travels through the inhomogeneous medium [*Elmore and Heald, 1969*]. Thus when partial reflections do occur it is not appropriate to use a WKB solution. However, partial reflections can be studied by considering step discontinuities.

3.5.3 Step Discontinuities

The other approximation that is used for inhomogeneous media involves step discontinuities. The effect of such inhomogeneities can be understood in terms of partial reflections. Non-equally spaced harmonics may occur in this case because each standing wave pattern must be a construction of the full-length waveform and the reflected portions.

Consider as an example the simple case of a single step discontinuity in the middle of a string of length L as shown in Figure 3.3. Since the velocity is inversely proportional to the square root of the density, such a step halves the velocity for half of the length for the values given. Ignoring the effects of partial reflections we may obtain approximate eigenvalue frequency solutions using time of flight calculations.

Let the velocity of the wave on the string of unitary linear density be v_1 . Then the velocity of the wave on the string of density $\rho = 4$ is $v_1/2$. For a fixed frequency, halving the velocity of the wave must half the wavelength. For the stepped density string, the wavelength of a transverse wave must be halved as it passes into the right

Figure 3.4: Comparison of the precise harmonic series for the string shown in Figure 3.3 with the harmonic series found by ignoring partial reflections.

hand side of the string. The effect of this is the same as leaving the velocity constant and simply doubling the length of the right hand half of the string.

Thus we can replace the stepped string of length L with a uniform string of length $L' = \frac{3}{2}L$ and calculate the expected resonant frequencies. For resonance we require

$$n\lambda = 2L' = 2 \cdot \frac{3}{2}L = 3L$$

and from $v = f\lambda$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} f &= \frac{v_1}{\lambda} \\ \therefore f_n &= \frac{nv_1}{3L} \end{aligned} .$$

These harmonics are evenly spaced since they were calculated for a substituted string of uniform density. It is easily seen that these harmonic frequencies are simply the harmonics of a uniform string with $\rho = 1$, multiplied through by a factor of $\frac{2}{3}$.

This linear harmonic series, along with the actual harmonic frequencies that were calculated numerically, is shown in Figure 3.4. The actual eigenvalues deviate from a linear series so that the ratios of one harmonic to another vary unpredictably from those expected for a uniform string. However, the actual harmonic series is still essentially a straight line.

The two harmonic series are superimposed for $n = 3, 6, 9, \dots$, as can be seen

Figure 3.5: Waveforms for the (a) third and (b) fourth harmonics oscillating on the string shown in Figure 3.3. Note that the third harmonic has a node at the discontinuity while the fourth harmonic does not..

Figure 3.6: String with half the length having $\rho = 1$ and the other half $\rho = 4$, but the low density segment centered.

in Figure 3.4. This suggests that partial reflections do not affect these resonant frequencies. Every third harmonic has a number of half wavelengths that is divisible by 3. The effect of the density step is to redistribute the waveform between each half of the string in a one-third/two-thirds manner, and so any harmonic which neatly divides by 3 will end up with a node at the density discontinuity. The partial reflections which are set up will be exactly in phase with the original wave, and so it is easy to understand why they don't cause the frequency of these harmonics to deviate.

Consider the string shown in Figure 3.6, again with one half of density $\rho = 1$ and the other with $\rho = 4$ but with the low density region in the middle of the string. The harmonic series for this string is shown in Figure 3.7, and every third harmonic again lines up with the line predicted by ignoring partial reflections. The other harmonics deviate from this line in a different manner to what they did for the previous case.

Non-linear harmonic series result from partial reflections of the wave, and the position of the reflection points alters the way that the harmonics deviate from a straight line.

Figure 3.7: Comparison of the precise harmonic series for the string shown in Figure 3.6 with the harmonic series found by ignoring partial reflections.

3.5.4 Continuously Varying Density

The intermediate situation where density variations are not slow enough to satisfy the WKB approximation, and not sharp enough to be analysed in terms of partially reflecting discontinuities, has not been well studied due to its complexity. The object of interest to remote magnetosphere density sensing is the behaviour of the harmonics for such a wave medium.

Consider the case of a density variation in the middle of a string as an example. Figure 3.8 shows a uniform density profile and a profile with a central trough, along with the resulting harmonic series. An explanation that involves harmonics being most dependent on the mass density at their antinodes, such as illustrated in Figure 3.1, would predict that the central density minimum leaves even harmonics essentially unchanged and causes the odd harmonics to alter. This would be evident by the odd and even harmonics forming separate lines in the harmonic series. However, it is evident from Figure 3.8(b) that the reduction of density in the middle of the string has little effect on any of the harmonic frequencies. The deviation of a set of points y_i a linear regression Y_i may be measured by

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (y_i - Y_i)^2}{N}} . \quad (3.11)$$

The harmonic series from the uniform string was linear as expected ($\sigma = 0.002$), and

Figure 3.8: (a) Density profiles for a stretched string, the solid line indicating a uniform string and the dashed line a density trough at the middle of the string. (b) The resulting harmonic series for these two density profiles. It is clear that the central trough affects all harmonics, and that the harmonic series are both essentially linear.

Figure 3.9: (a) Highly varying density profile for a stretched string, and (b) the resulting harmonic series and its linear regression. The harmonic series is not linear, but the deviation is only small.

the harmonic series from the peaked density profile deviated from a straight line by $\sigma = 0.128$.

Careful examination of the harmonic series in Figure 3.8 reveals that the second harmonic does in fact change with a smaller proportion than the other frequencies. This effect becomes more noticeable as the density variation becomes more prominent, as is shown in Figure 3.9. However, even for this highly non-uniform density profile the harmonic series deviates from a straight line by only $\sigma = 0.694$.

As was seen in Section 3.5.3, non-linear harmonic series arise when the wave is partially reflected from regions other than the ends of the medium. As the density becomes more varied, the WKB approximation no longer applies and partial reflections become significant. Even in those cases where partial reflections do cause the harmonic series to deviate from a straight line, this deviation is proportionately much smaller than the corresponding density inhomogeneities from which it results.

The implications of this for realistic magnetospheric density profiles are explored in Chapter 5.

Not all of the features of harmonic variation have been explained. For example, it is not understood how a linear harmonic series with extrapolated frequency intercept other than zero could arise, but these are commonly observed.

Chapter 4

GOES Magnetometer Data

The suite of 5 GOES satellites operating during 2003 provided measurements of geomagnetic pulsations at geosynchronous orbit. The data presented here was sampled at 2 Hz, a high resolution not commonly available, and harmonic structure in the ULF band was often visible during the local morning.

At times the GOES spacecraft are relocated in longitude, and as two satellites passed a rare opportunity for concurrent measurement was presented. Measurements from closely positioned satellites gave some insight into the spatial structure of the resonances.

Approximate date	Satellites involved	Longitudinal location
May 1	GOES 8 and GOES 12	77° West
June 3	GOES 8 and GOES 11	114° West
June 26	GOES 8 and GOES 10	136° West

Table 4.1: GOES satellite cross-over events during 2003. The indicated day of crossing is approximate and was calculated by assuming a longitudinal speed of one degree per day for moving GOES satellites to interpolate between monthly position information.

4.1 The GOES Spacecraft

The Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) program has the primary purpose of providing weather imagery for the United States of America. The first satellite under the GOES program was launched in October 1975, and there have been 12 successful GOES satellites so far. At any particular time there are typically 3-5 operational GOES satellites in orbit. There is usually one operational satellite in the “east” position (75° west) and one in the “west” position (135° west).

Weather information is provided by the Imager and Sounder instruments on board the GOES spacecraft. The GOES Imager detects radiant and reflected energy from sampled areas of the Earth, and sweeps through a scan sequence to provide various sized images. The Sounder collects data from which atmospheric and surface temperature, water content profiles and ozone distribution can be calculated. In addition, the satellites are equipped with a Solar X-Ray Imager that is used to monitor solar activity and provide warning information about events that could harm space and ground systems.

Occasionally the GOES satellites are moved in longitude. When one GOES spacecraft passes by another it provides the opportunity for multiple measurements to be taken at almost the same point, a luxury in space physics. Table 4.1 lists the cross-over events that occurred during 2003. Further details of the GOES program may be found online at <http://goespoes.gsfc.nasa.gov/goes/index.html>.

4.2 Magnetometer Data

The data presented in this thesis were collected by the 3-axis fluxgate magnetometers on board GOES 8-12 during 2003, and are analysed in the spacecraft coordinate frame. This is a cylindrical coordinate system (H_p, H_e, H_n) where H_p is parallel to the Earth’s spin axis for a zero inclination orbit, which is approximately parallel to the magnetic field in the equatorial plane, H_e is directed Earthward, and H_n is directed eastward to complete the orthogonal system [Fraser *et al.*, 2005].

This investigation presents data that had a sampling frequency of 2 Hz, higher than is typically available from the GOES magnetometer telemetry. These data were

supplied by Professor Howard Singer at the NOAA Space Environment Centre, and included more than 100 days of measurements from 2001 and 2003. Not all of the 5 GOES satellites in space during this period were operating all the time, but there was always an operating spacecraft in the East and West longitudinal positions. In total, more than 300 day files were examined for events of interest.

The following features were sought in the magnetometer data:

- Most of the satellites operating during the event, to provide data from as many longitudinal locations as possible;
- A large number of visible harmonics, to maximise the possible information that could be obtained from the resonances;
- Two GOES at similar longitudes, to explore concurrent measurements in space.

There was some trade off between these criteria. For instance, the day with the most harmonics observed had data from only two satellites, and some days when all 5 satellites were operational showed clear harmonic structure only at a few spacecraft. Six events were chosen for detailed investigation, and these are shown in Table 4.2.

The most precise GOES position information available was a list of longitudes at the first day of each month, which was mostly satisfactory for the geostationary satellites. For any of the spacecraft undergoing longitudinal relocation it was necessary to interpolate between the specified monthly positions in order to estimate the measurement location. Typical relocation speeds were about 1 degree in longitude per day. Another difficulty in obtaining the information listed in Table 4.2 was that the lower order harmonics usually started earlier and persisted longer than the higher order harmonics, making it difficult to neatly specify the duration of the resonance event. The indicated times are the approximate duration of the highest visible harmonic.

4.3 A Typical Event: June 26, 2003

June 26, 2003, offered an occasion when all 5 GOES were operational. GOES 8 and GOES 10 were close to each other at longitudes of 137 and 136 degrees west respectively, and recorded 5 well defined Pc3-4 harmonics. Each of the other satellites recorded 3 or more harmonics.

Dynamic spectra were generated over 0-1 Hz by computing the Fourier transforms of 20 minute data windows with a 50% overlap. The dynamic spectra of the azimuthal component of the data from GOES 8 and 10 are shown in Figure 4.1. The band structure visible in the right hand side of these plots indicates stable and nearly regularly spaced spectral peaks.

Date	GOES	Time of observed harmonics		Longitude (degrees West)
		Hours UT	Hours LT	
June 26 DOY 177	8	16 - 19	7 - 10	137
	9	1 - 6	11 - 16	205
	10	16 - 19	7 - 10	136
	11	17 - 22	9 - 14	113
	12	15 - 20	10 - 15	75
February 17 DOY 48	8	10 - 18	5 - 13	75
	10	15 - 23	6 - 14	135
	12	12 - 22	6 - 16	95
February 19 DOY 50	8	11 - 18	6 - 13	75
	10	15 - 22	6 - 15	135
	12	12 - 21	6 - 15	95
June 30 DOY 181	8	16 - 18	7 - 9	141
	9	19 - 24	5 - 10	205
	10	16 - 21	7 - 12	136
	11	16 - 22	8 - 14	113
	12	13 - 20	8 - 15	75
May 7 DOY 127	8	12 - 17	6 - 11	83
	9	17 - 24	3 - 10	208
	10	15 - 19	6 - 10	135
March 22 DOY 81	8	13 - 21	7 - 16	75
	10	15 - 22	6 - 13	136
	12	13 - 23	7 - 17	84

Table 4.2: Events chosen from 2003 for detailed investigation, shown in decreasing order of satisfying all criteria. The calculated local time (LT) durations of the harmonic structure are approximate and are included to indicate the tendency for ULF harmonics to be observed in the local morning sector.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.1: Dynamic power spectra for (a) GOES 8 and (b) GOES 10 on June 26, 2003, showing the azimuthal component H_n . The band structure from about 1700 UT to the end of the day is characteristic of FLR harmonics. The vertical blue stripe near 2000 UT for GOES 8 was a gap in the data from this satellite.

The frequencies of these bands are in the ULF band, and are similar to the values calculated by *Cummings et al.* [1969] for FLR harmonics. Furthermore, shear Alfvén mode oscillations are expected to be predominantly in the azimuthal component and the band structure is absent in the field-aligned and radial components, as shown in Figure 4.2. These observations support the conclusion that the bands indicate toroidal mode FLR harmonics.

4.3.1 Measurement Uncertainties

4.3.1.1 Technical Limitations

The frequency resolution for FFT spectral results is given by

$$\Delta f = \frac{1}{N\Delta t} \quad (4.1)$$

where N is the number of samples for each FFT and Δt is the time interval between samples. For the 2 Hz GOES magnetometer data, a 20 minute data window has $\Delta f = 0.833$ mHz, which is approximately 15% of typical fundamental frequencies.

Using a shorter FFT length would improve time resolution but reduce frequency resolution. For example, using a 3 minute FFT length would give rise to a frequency resolution of $\Delta f = 5.56$ mHz, which is approximately equal to typical fundamental frequencies. Since the resonant frequencies remained fairly constant and the pulsations lasted for hours, it was appropriate to trade time resolution for frequency resolution. These are limitations introduced by the Fourier transform process on digital data.

In reality, the spectral peaks were often sufficiently broad that the peak covered a number of Δf intervals which further increased the uncertainty of frequency measurement. For constant frequencies it is possible to improve frequency estimates by averaging, as was done for the Fourier transforms of the 20 minute windows. Some studies have estimated frequencies by averaging across many samples from different days [*Takahashi et al.*, 2004, 2006]. Such a process assumes that the actual resonances at the measurement location stay at fixed frequencies for a period encompassing all of the samples, and is not useful for probing shorter duration magnetospheric events.

4.3.1.2 Spectral Analysis

The measured harmonic frequencies and their uncertainties are shown against time in Figure 4.3. The results are very similar for these two satellites, which was expected due to their close proximity. The five most clearly visible harmonics were within the 5-45 mHz band. They remained relatively constant throughout the event, which justifies taking an average spectrum over a time period of a few hours. The period

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.2: Dynamic power spectra for data recorded by GOES 10 on June 26, 2003, showing (a) the field-aligned component H_p and (b) the radial component H_e . The harmonic structure clearly visible in the azimuthal component shown in Figure 4.1 is notably missing from these components.

Figure 4.3: Harmonic frequencies for GOES 8 and GOES 10 on June 26, 2003. The GOES 8 points are shown at the beginning of the hour they represent, and the GOES 10 points for the same hour are shown displaced to the right for clarity.

with the most well defined harmonic structure was the three hours between 16 and 19 UT, partly due to the gap in data from GOES 8. Averaging the overlapping 20 minute windows across this three hour period gave the power spectra shown in Figure 4.4, from which it is clear that GOES 8 and 10 measured the same resonant frequencies.

The frequency uncertainties from the average spectra are at least ± 1 mHz for each harmonic. The fundamental harmonic was measured to have a frequency of 5.4 ± 1.0 mHz. Although the hourly averages only identified five harmonics, the three-hour average power spectra in Figure 4.4 shows a further continuation of peaks. These have been numbered in italics to indicate that they are not as distinct as the first five, but were measured and recorded.

4.3.2 Linearity of Harmonic Series

Although the long-lasting stable peaks in the azimuthal component dynamic spectra may be identified as resonances, there is no indication of which harmonic order to assign to each frequency. The most direct way to determine harmonic order is to

Figure 4.4: Power spectra for GOES 8 and GOES 10 for 16 - 19 UT on June 26, 2003. The harmonic order assigned is indicated above each peak, and the last three harmonics are indicated in italics because they are less distinct and were not identified in the hourly averages.

examine the number of nodes in the standing waveform, but this cannot be measured for magnetospheric FLRs.

Even though symmetric field lines, as are usually assumed when modelling the geomagnetic field, result in a central node for every even harmonic, the tilt of the Earth's magnetic axis with respect to its rotational axis means that geosynchronous satellites should in general detect even harmonics. In fact, it is unlikely that the mass density along geomagnetic field lines is symmetric, which further increases the chances of GOES spacecraft detecting even harmonics. It is thus reasonable to expect that the spectral peaks observed in GOES magnetometer data are adjacent harmonics.

Extensive modelling of realistic mass density profiles discussed in Chapter 3 revealed that harmonic series consistently remained close to linear. It is thus also reasonable to expect the measured harmonics to be approximately evenly spaced, and to attribute sharp steps in measured harmonic series to missing harmonics. A natural peak in the noise spectrum at low frequencies made it difficult to identify the fundamental. However, if the spacing between resonant frequencies was approximately equal to the lowest harmonic frequency then it was assumed that the fundamental had been identified correctly. A lowest harmonic with frequency much higher than the typical spacing would indicate one or more harmonics missing at the lower end of the series.

Using these lines of reasoning, harmonic order was assigned to the observed spectral peaks by first assuming that the lowest observed frequency was the fundamental, then by assuming each subsequent peak to be the next harmonic, and finally by removing any kinks in the harmonic series that could be explained by a missing harmonic. The harmonic series identified in this manner from the power spectra in Figure 4.4 was found to be the same for both GOES 8 and GOES 10, and is shown in Figure 4.5.

A linear regression was fitted to this series of eight points, and the deviation from a straight line was calculated using equation (3.11) to be $\sigma = 0.683$. The first five harmonics, which were more reliably identified from the data, were found to deviate from a linear regression by only $\sigma = 0.105$. The high linearity of the observed harmonic series concurs with results from modelling. This does not seem to be a special case, and Figure 4.6 shows other experimental harmonic series which are close to linear.

4.3.3 Azimuthal Variation

The ideal toroidal mode for a dipole field, as illustrated in Figure 2.1, would result in identical FLR frequencies being observed at geosynchronous orbit regardless of longitude. However, the harmonic series shown in Figure 4.6 show that the GOES

Figure 4.5: Harmonic series for both GOES 8 and GOES 10 for the 3-hour period 1600 - 1900 UT on June 26, 2003. The dashed line is the linear regression of the first five harmonics, which was found to have the form $y = 8.9x - 3.4$, and the observed harmonics deviate from this by only $\sigma = 0.105$. The dotted line is the linear regression of all eight points, with the form $y = 8.4x - 2.2$ and a standard deviation for the data of $\sigma = 0.683$. The top three points were not identified in the hourly averages shown in Figure 4.3, but were visible in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.6: Harmonic series from GOES satellites for (a) February 19 and (b) June 30, 2003. The measured frequencies form an almost linear harmonic series in every case. The frequency uncertainties have been omitted for clarity, but are at least as large as those shown in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.7: Average cross-power (solid line) and empirical noise threshold (dashed curve) for GOES 8 and 10 on June 26, 2003. The function chosen as a threshold was $0.00003 \times f^{-1}$.

satellites did not necessarily record the same resonant frequencies during the same day. The longitudinal variation in resonant frequencies was used to explore the azimuthal FLR structure.

4.3.3.1 GOES 8 and GOES 10

On June 26, 2003, GOES 8 and 10 were separated by about 1 degree in longitude. Due to their proximity, they recorded identical harmonic frequencies as shown in Figure 4.4. The azimuthal wave number m of oscillations may be determined by examining the phase difference (cross-phase) at resonant frequencies between the two measurements.

The FFT provides values for the spectral cross-phase, even for noise. For the purposes of investigating FLRs, any signal that was not part of the harmonic series was considered to be noise. To ensure that the cross-phase was only measured where there was strong resonance signal, a low cross-power threshold was determined. The non-resonance background spectrum was found by averaging the cross-power calculated for 20 minute data windows over an entire day, and a $f^{-\gamma}$ function was matched to this curve. This exponential function was used as a noise threshold, and refined by visually verifying that the harmonics evident on the dynamic cross-power were obvious in the cross-phase obtained. The final threshold was given by $0.00003 \times f^{-1}$, and is shown superimposed on the average cross-power in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.8: Cross phase between GOES 8 and GOES 10 on June 26, 2003. The green area indicates where the cross power was lower than a threshold matched to the average noise. The resonances were observed during 16 - 19 UT, and this period shows relatively small cross-phase at the resonant frequencies.

The cross-phase was measured for each resonance by averaging all of the measurements from points where the power was above the threshold. The total measurement period was matched to the duration of the resonance. The dynamic cross phase spectra between GOES 8 and 10 is shown in Figure 4.8. A positive phase difference means that the signal from GOES 10 lagged behind that from GOES 8. The cross phase measured between these satellites varied for each harmonic, and ranged from -5° for the fundamental to about 8° for higher order harmonics, as shown in Table 4.3. The standard deviation of these cross-phase measurements was about 10° . These results, and their uncertainty, are discussed in Section 5.1.

4.3.3.2 The Other Satellites

If larger phase differences could be measured with the same standard deviation it would decrease the relative uncertainty of the results. For a fixed azimuthal structure, the only way to measure larger phase differences would be to use more distantly spaced satellites.

The power spectra computed from data for each GOES during the observed period of FLR harmonics are shown in Figure 4.9, and it is apparent that the only curves that match are those from GOES 8 and 10. Although GOES 11 was at a longitude of 113 degrees west, angularly separated from GOES 10 by only 23

Harmonic order	Frequency	Average cross phase	Standard deviation
1	5.0	-5.2	11
	5.83	-4.1	10
2	14.167	2.4	9.4
	15.0	3.1	9.0
3	23.3	7.6	13
	24.167	8.0	9.7
4	31.67	11	12
	32.5	6.1	11
5	40.83	6.3	16
	41.67	7.3	17

Table 4.3: Cross-phase data from 1600-1900 hours on June 26, 2003 for GOES 8 and GOES 10. The resonance peaks covered multiple Δf intervals, and so the two data points closest to the middle of the peak were recorded to give some indication of the reliability of the phase difference measurement.

degrees, these two satellites measured slightly different resonant frequencies. The satellites which were more widely separated in longitude also measured different resonant frequencies.

Since a measurement of spectral cross-phase at the resonant frequencies depends on each spectrum having peaks at the same position, it was not possible to measure cross-phase between satellites separated by more than a few degrees in longitude.

Figure 4.9: Power spectra from all 5 GOES during the observed periods of FLR.

Chapter 5

Discussion

The process and primary results of numerically modelling resonant frequencies for various density profiles and the nature of the GOES data have been described. The modelling showed that harmonic frequencies are insensitive to changes in field line mass density profile, and this makes it difficult to use FLR observations to probe the magnetosphere. Harmonic spacing is particularly insensitive to smooth density variations far from the equator, but may be affected by sharp discontinuities causing partial reflections.

5.1 Estimating Azimuthal Structure

The phase differences between data from GOES 8 and 10 at resonant frequencies for the event of June 26, 2003, were measured in Section 4.3.3 to be small (less than 10 degrees). These two satellites were separated by approximately one degree in longitude, and so from equation (2.24) we can estimate the azimuthal wave number to be less than 10. The uncertainties of about 10 degrees in the cross-phase measurements were proportionally large, but do not suggest an azimuthal wave number greater than 20. As outlined in Section 2.2.2, the reason for measuring the azimuthal wave number m was to obtain information about the toroidal FLR excitation mechanisms. Although measurement uncertainties made it impossible to obtain a particular value for m , the results exclude high- m mechanisms such as drift-bounce resonance.

GOES 10 and 11 were separated by only 23° longitudinally. The comparison of spectra from each satellite shown in Figure 4.9 indicated that these satellites measured different resonant frequencies, and this made it impossible to determine the azimuthal wave number. Data from GOES separated by greater distances were analysed, and found to show similar differences in the resonant frequencies.

The concept of L -shells, which oscillate azimuthally in the toroidal mode as illustrated in Figure 2.1, may be extended to less regular “ L -surfaces” when dealing with magnetic fields deviating from an ideal dipole geometry. It is likely that the geomagnetic field deviates from a perfectly dipolar geometry and this means that geosynchronous satellites at different longitudes may be on different “ L -surfaces” even though they are at the same geocentric distance. Since the field line length is different for each L -surface, this would explain the observation of slightly different FLR frequencies at different longitudes on the GOES geosynchronous orbit.

If the separated GOES spacecraft are on different L -surfaces then the closeness of the resonant frequencies which are measured suggests a continuum of frequencies resonating adjacent to each other. The simple model of oscillating shells adjacent to each other is inadequate. Some work has already begun on investigating this, involving phase mixing [Wright *et al.*, 1999].

Another possible explanation is that the longitudinal mass loading structure is localised rather than global. This could give rise to various frequencies of resonance (from dominant L -surfaces) at various longitudinal positions around the Earth.

5.2 Harmonic Dependence on Density

As mentioned in Section 3.4.2, and illustrated in Figure 3.1, it has often been claimed that each harmonic responds independently to local density variations [Denton *et al.*, 2001, 2004; Takahashi *et al.*, 2004, 2006; Takahashi, 2006]. This concept has led

people to consider harmonic ratios rather than consider the harmonics as a series. It has also contributed to the idea that each successive harmonic contributes further information about the mass density profile along the oscillating field line.

The competing idea is that harmonics remain almost evenly spaced for realistic density distributions, and the resulting linear harmonic series can yield only two independent parameters regardless of how many harmonics are observed. The time of flight approximation explored in Section 3.5.2 was found to result in harmonics which are integer multiples of the fundamental frequency whenever the WKB approximation is valid.

The harmonics observed in GOES magnetometer data were found to deviate from a linear series by much less than their measurement uncertainties.

5.2.1 Examining Some Non-Linear Results

An early suggestion that harmonics may vary independently came from a graph published by *Poulter et al.* [1988]. For small L and large L the harmonics were found to be evenly spaced, but there was a region in the middle where the harmonics became unevenly spaced. These results were reproduced, and a plot of harmonic frequency against time for the first 12 harmonics is shown in Figure 5.1. Investigation revealed that the density profiles peaked sharply just before the ends and decayed away toward each end as shown in Figure 5.2. While it is true that the density of charged particles peaks in the ionosphere and then decreases with decreasing altitude, the mass density continues to increase through the atmosphere to the Earth's surface.

In Section 3.5.3 it was found that sharp discontinuities can cause the harmonics to become unevenly spaced. In order to investigate the effect of the sharp density peaks in the density profile it was assumed that reflection occurred from the point of maximum density. This had the effect of removing the decreasing ends from the density profile. The first 12 harmonics were calculated for these cropped density profiles, and are shown plotted against time in Figure 5.3. Comparison with Figure 5.1 shows that the cropped density profiles produce more evenly spaced harmonics.

The harmonics are not exactly evenly spaced even for the cropped density profiles. However, the uncertainties associated with measuring harmonic frequencies (as discussed for the GOES data in Section 4.3.1) make it difficult to observe small deviations from a straight line in the harmonic series.

Figure 5.1: (a) Unevenly spaced harmonics as reported by *Poulter et al.* [1988]. For most of the day the harmonics were approximately evenly spaced, but the first 7 hours show uneven spacing particularly in the lower order harmonics. (b) Harmonic series for $LT = 4$ and 12.

Figure 5.2: Sample density profile for the unevenly spaced harmonics of *Poulter et al.* [1988]. The sharp peaks near each end were found to distort the harmonics series.

5.3 Level of Sensitivity

5.3.1 Power Law Solution Space

It was noted in Section 3.5.4 that large changes to the density profile result in small variations of the resonant frequencies. The solution space for the power law density model (2.20) was mapped for typical harmonic frequencies in order to examine the level of sensitivity of FLR frequencies to changes in magnetospheric density profiles.

The power law density model has only two parameters, ρ_{eq} and α , and so for a given harmonic series one of these parameters can be fixed and an optimum value obtained for the other parameter. Systematically choosing several values of the the index α and obtaining corresponding optimum values for the equatorial density ρ_{eq} allowed a solution space to be mapped for a given harmonic series. For a sequence of α values, the optimum ρ_{eq} was found by iteratively adjusting the value to minimise the deviation of the measured harmonic series from the calculated frequencies. In the power law model, the equatorial density ρ_{eq} is a multiplicative factor. It was found that varying this parameter multiplied not only the density profile but also the harmonic series through by a constant. This behaviour of the power law model meant that for any α value, a unique ρ_{eq} value could be found to best match the calculated harmonics to the measured frequencies.

A solution space was mapped by matching the modelled harmonics to the first five resonant frequencies recorded by GOES 8 and 10 on June 26, 2003, and is shown in Figure 5.4. The uncertainty margin for the equatorial density was calculated by matching the modelled harmonic series to the most extreme lines encompassed by the error bars on the measured frequencies. Reducing the number of harmonics

Figure 5.3: (a) The first 12 harmonics plotted against time for density profiles cropped at the maxima, and (b) harmonic series for $LT = 4$ and 12 . The harmonics are more evenly spaced than in Figure 5.1, indicating that the sharp density peaks produced artifacts in the harmonics series.

Figure 5.4: Solution space for the power law model. The data to which the predicted harmonic frequencies were matched came from GOES 8 and 10 on June 26, 2003. The dashed lines indicate the uncertainty margin resulting from optimally matching the first five harmonics to the observed series.

that were matched had the effect of increasing the uncertainty in optimal equatorial density for a given power law index.

The range in equatorial density is only one order of magnitude over α values between 0 and 10. This indicates the lack of sensitivity of the harmonics to the form of the density profile. A positive outcome of this insensitivity is that the use of this model to determine equatorial density when only the fundamental is observed is justified, since ρ_{eq} is almost independent of α for realistic assumptions (usually $0 \leq \alpha \leq 6$). The drawback of this lack of sensitivity is that measured harmonics do not provide detailed information about the density profile along a resonating field line, even when five eigenfrequencies are observed.

While originally it was thought that a power law index of $\alpha = 3 - 4$ was appropriate for $L \approx 6$, there have been a number of recent papers arguing that for geosynchronous field lines the best power law model has low $\alpha \approx 0 - 1$ [Takahashi *et al.*, 2004; Denton *et al.*, 2006]. Takahashi *et al.* [2006] adopted an $\alpha = 0.5$ model to determine mass density from toroidal frequencies, basing this choice on work by Takahashi *et al.* [2004]. The results shown in Figures 5.4 and 5.5 suggest that the precise value of this index is of limited importance.

In order to obtain realistic values of the density near the ionosphere the International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) was used. It was found that α values as high as 8 were required to obtain density profiles with equatorial densities that gave the measured harmonic frequencies and ionospheric densities that matched the IRI model. Given that the harmonics do not depend on the density far from the equator, and the significant measurement uncertainties of observed resonances, it is perhaps more reasonable to obtain α in this fashion than to seek optimum matching of harmonic

Figure 5.5: Optimally matched power law profiles for assumed values of α between -1 and 6 inclusive. It is clear that the harmonics are far less dependent on density far from the equator than they are on the equatorial density.

frequencies.

5.3.2 Lack of Sensitivity off the Equatorial Plane

Another way to express the solution space mapped in Figure 5.4 is to consider all of the density profiles which produce harmonics close to the observed frequencies. The optimal power law profiles for $-1 \leq \alpha \leq 6$ are shown in Figure 5.5. It is apparent that although the optimum equatorial density is almost independent of α , varying the index makes a large difference to the density profile far from the equator.

This enhanced dependence on the density near the equator has long been known, and can be attributed to the Alfvén velocity profile [Poulter *et al.*, 1988]. For typical density distributions, the geomagnetic field is such that the Alfvén speed decreases with radius and is at a minimum near the equatorial plane. The time of flight approximate calculation using equation (3.10) indicates that the resonant frequencies are most affected by the region in which they spend the most time, which is where the velocity is lowest.

From a statistical study of the first three harmonics detected by the Combined Release and Radiation Effects Satellite (CRRES), Denton *et al.* [2006] reported finding a local peak in the plasma mass density near the equator at geosynchronous

orbit. They provided frequency ratio data for the first three harmonics, but did not indicate what the fundamental frequency actually was. For the reasonable assumption of a fundamental frequency at $f_1 = 8$ mHz, the next two eigenfrequencies were calculated from the given ratios to be $f_2 = 22 (\pm 3)$ mHz and $f_3 = 34 (\pm 5)$ mHz. The uncertainties represent about 14% of the harmonic frequencies, and were calculated from the uncertainties listed by *Denton et al.* [2006].

Using the density model constructed from the Bernstein 6-basis (3.9), a number of density profiles were found that yielded harmonic frequencies close to the data. Some of these plausible density profiles are shown in Figure 5.6. Parameters were adjusted to produce a centrally enhanced density profile close to that shown in Figure 8 of *Denton et al.* [2006], and this is indicated by the solid line.

Other centrally enhanced profiles were tested, and it was found that the harmonics were not at all sensitive to the width of the local equatorial maximum. In order to test validity of concluding an equatorial density enhancement, a profile was created which had an equatorial depletion and two local maxima either side of the equator. This profile produced harmonics closely matching the three data points, and well within the stated uncertainty margins. Discarding the assumption of hemispherical symmetry resulted in an even wider variety of density profiles which produced matching harmonics, but these are not shown.

It seems that the assertion of an equatorial enhancement is a result of the form chosen for the density model. With the more general Bernstein 6-basis, as with the simple power law, plausible density profiles have similar equatorial values but differ significantly at higher latitudes. Even at the equator, significant changes in density accompany only small changes in harmonic frequencies. These effects combine to make it impossible to use harmonics to probe the field-line density anywhere beyond about 15 degrees from the magnetic equator.

These results seem to contradict the effect discussed in Section 5.2.1 for the unevenly spaced harmonics calculated by *Poulter et al.* [1988], but they were a case of sharp density changes causing reflections. Although the density far from the equator has very little effect on the harmonic frequencies, sharp discontinuities even near the ends of the field line can give rise to partial reflections which alter the corresponding frequencies. Essentially, the density far from the equator can vary smoothly across multiple orders of magnitude without affecting the harmonics, but if variations introduce sharp boundaries the harmonics may be affected.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.6: (a) Plausible density profiles for the harmonic ratio data given in *Denton et al.* [2006] (latitude in radians), and (b) the corresponding harmonic series compared to the data points indicated by diamonds. The solid line indicates a density profile created using the Bernstein 6-basis model to match the profile found by *Denton et al.* [2006] using the model in equation (3.7).

Chapter 6

Conclusion

Field line resonances do depend on plasma density, but not in a well behaved way. In order to use observed harmonics to probe density, highly accurate measurements are required to overcome significant uncertainty propagation. The velocity profile means that in most cases it is impossible to use resonant frequencies to determine mass density away from the magnetic equator.

Analysing observed eigenfrequencies in terms of the harmonic series provides a clearer view of the information available than does investigating frequency ratios. Interesting areas for further study include testing the sensitivity of FLR harmonics to a known density perturbation such as a plasmasphere plume.

6.1 Deriving Density From FLR Harmonics

While almost every previous study has looked exclusively at the independent harmonic ratios, the realisation that FLR harmonics remain close to evenly spaced suggests that information is most reliably read from the harmonic series as a whole. A simple plot of harmonic frequency against harmonic order produces a series of points which were found to be almost collinear for the GOES magnetometer data analysed, and to remain close to linear for realistic modelled density profiles. The slope and intercept of this series provide the only information contained in the sequence of resonant frequencies.

The fact that harmonics are almost evenly spaced allows observed FLR frequencies to be assigned a harmonic number relatively easily. Although additional harmonics do not provide much extra information about the density profile, they help to specify the shape of the harmonic series with greater accuracy. This increases the precision to which density information may be obtained, and so observing high numbers of harmonics remains advantageous.

For $L = 6.6$ field lines, the FLR frequencies are dependent predominantly on the density within 15 degrees of the magnetic equator. This lack of dependence on the density far from the equator has been recognised before, but has been underestimated by those who expect to use harmonics to learn anything about the mass density far from the equatorial plane. This makes it impossible to achieve one of the original goals of FLR analysis [*Price et al.*, 1999; *Denton et al.*, 2001].

6.2 Data From the GOES Spacecraft

The 2 Hz magnetometer data from the 5 GOES spacecraft were found to be very useful for studying FLRs at geosynchronous orbit. Having 5 spacecraft at the same geocentric radius with various longitudinal separations allowed an investigation of the azimuthal structure of toroidal FLRs. It was found that only spacecraft with a small azimuthal separation actually recorded the same eigenfrequencies. This made it impossible to compare the phase of resonances between widely spaced satellites, which limited the conclusions that could be made about the azimuthal wave number. However, even when the large uncertainties in phase difference were taken into account the results indicated an azimuthal wavenumber less than 20. This excludes excitation mechanisms such as drift-bounce resonance.

6.3 Potential for Further Study

6.3.1 Modelling the Effect of Density Models

It was suggested in Section 5.3.2 that the local enhancement of mass density in the equatorial region reported by *Denton et al.* [2006] was an artifact of the density model used (given in equation (3.7)). It would be possible to test this by calculating harmonics for a density profile created using unrelated mathematical functions (such as a cosine curve), and matching frequencies from other modelled profiles to these values. It might be possible to ascertain whether certain model functions are more likely to suggest various phenomena such as equatorial enhancements.

6.3.2 Harmonic Fluctuations Near Plasmasphere Plumes

The Image EUV experiment identified a number of plasmasphere plume events. If a plume event could be found from which there was also GOES magnetic field data as one or more of these geosynchronous satellites passed through the plume, then a test would be possible.

If there was a frequency change then it would be possible to analyse the sensitivity and again make a judgement of the effectiveness of the method. If there was no noticeable change in the harmonic frequencies, this would demonstrate that the technique was too insensitive for mass density probing. It could also be concluded that the plume was not in the equatorial plane (due to the insensitivity of harmonics to high latitude density, as mentioned above).

A difficulty with this type of investigation is that plumes are almost always observed in the local evening and through to midnight, while ULF harmonics are most regularly observed in the local morning.

Appendix A

Abstract presented at AIP Congress 2006

Geomagnetic field lines in the Earth's magnetosphere and plasmasphere when perturbed may resonate like a violin string, giving rise to ultra-low frequency (ULF) hydromagnetic wave field line resonance (FLR). Through studying mass loading in FLR it is possible to remotely determine the plasma mass density in these regions. In the past there have been a number of attempts to develop a technique for probing plasmaspheric densities using observed ULF field line resonance harmonic structure, but most assume a plasma density model. A more accurate method for achieving this would be to allow fine temporal resolution magnetosphere density models to be constructed, rather than assumed, from a practical number of measurements.

In developing this technique further, the fundamental relationship between flux tube density and FLR harmonic frequencies has been explored. In this paper some of this fundamental but elusive physics is presented. Parameterised density models of a number of forms were examined, and the Bernstein basis polynomials were found to be particularly useful due to the spatial significance of the plasma model parameters. The effect of hemispherical asymmetry was explored theoretically, to find out if it should be possible to use resonance harmonics to identify such asymmetry.

A refined technique for determining the density profile of a flux tube from FLR harmonic frequencies has been developed. Better convergence on density profile parameter solutions was sought by requiring less information from the harmonic series than has previously been expected. We present results from testing this technique on Pc3-4 (10-100 mHz) ULF wave data from the GOES geostationary satellites. The situation with one GOES satellite slowly drifting azimuthally past another provided the opportunity to examine measurements from two spacecraft at almost the same location.

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